

Social taboos and resource management among the Nyishi of Kurung Kumey, Arunachal Pradesh

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Indigenous communities such as the Nyishi have historically managed their natural resources based on traditional knowledge, beliefs and practices for generations. Berkes (2012) calls such interdependence a ‘Knowledge-Practice- Belief’ system. Turner and Berkes (2006), Menzies and Butler (2006) and Berkes (2012) note that in such societies, resource management systems are closely tied to the beliefs and cosmology which shape the worldview and guide management practices through norms and taboos. Taboos are thus self-imposed by the community and strongly resonate with resource access, use and broader management practices. Taboos have social and personal aspects; they must be observed at both levels to ensure compliance. The taboos enumerated here indicate individual and social aspects of the Nyishi society.

This paper uses Colding and Folke’s Resource and Habitat Taboos (RHT) model to elucidate the social taboos of Nyishi in order to draw out the potential objectives behind them regarding resource management. The use of the model here is in the broadest sense. It thus includes taboos, rituals and beliefs as they are interrelated aspects for the Nyishi and have collective implications in resource management practices. Colding and Folke’s RHT model is based on the extensive review of literature on various practices around the world and, as such, is typecast into six categories – Species-specific taboos, life history taboos, segment taboos, temporal taboos, habitat taboos and method taboos (Colding & Folke, 2001). Thus, the paper highlights the interrelationship between taboos, resource management and conservation among the Nyishi of Kurung Kumey.

Keywords : Social Taboos, Resource Management, Conservation, Nyishi, Kurung Kumey.